

Ants — a natural enemy of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* larvae in dryland rice

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In upland areas of Batangas province, Philippines, where one crop of dryland rice/year is grown, the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenée) is the most important insect pest attacking the aboveground portions of the rice plant. But investigation of folded leaves in the 1978 season revealed very few larvae. Possible explanations were sought through field observations. Ants were found to leave their nests in underground tunnels and move up the rice foliage. They enter folded leaves and prey on larvae, carrying them between their mandibles back to the tunnels. One *Diacamma* sp. worker (see photo) was observed to transport 4–10 larvae/hour; its greatest activity is from 0900 to 1030 and from 1600 to 1730 hours.

Six ant species – *Camponotus* nr. *devestivus* Wheeler, *C.* nr. *nawai* Ito, *Diacamma* sp., *Odontomachus* sp., *Odontoponera transversa* (F. Smith), and *Solenopsis geminata* (F.) (identified by Dr. R. Sonobe, Japan) – were found to prey on the leaf folder larvae, but *Diacamma* sp. was the most abundant. Because of its greater prevalence, this species appears to be a better predator of leaf folder larvae than the carabid beetle *Chlaenius* sp. that we found during the 1977 season.

Photo. Adult of *Diacamma* sp. Hymenoptera: Formicidae.

International Rice Research Newsletter 1980 Volume 5 No. 4 pages 22-23.